

Interview questions with humanities researchers about constructing Digital Humanities Scholarly Commons at Beijing Normal University, China PRC

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1. Have you heard of digital humanities? If you heard that, when did you hear "digital humanities"?
2. If you have not heard of it, ask: Are you interested in learning about digital humanities? (Prepare the digital humanities papers of relevant disciplines and show them to the interviewees.)
3. Do you consider using text mining, GIS(Geographic information System) and social network relationship analysis to do your research? Have you encountered any difficulties?
4. In your research, which aspect of the difficulty is the biggest? (such as collecting relevant literature, technical obstacles)
5. Digital humanities involves the processing of data, from data collection, sorting, labeling, storage to data utilization, analysis, and presentation. Are you willing to let the librarian participate in your research project and make suggestions for your data management?
6. Are you willing to accept digital humanities-related embedded course training or project-specific training provided by the library?
7. Would you like to provide your research data to the library for backup, storage, and construction of the database? Would you like to share your research data to other researchers? To what extent are you willing to share your data? Will you share your data on campus or to any relevant researcher in the world?